

Compounds of $TiBr_4$ with Organic Substances in Non-aqueous Media

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Complex compounds of titanium tetrabromide with nitroanilines, amino-acids, aminophenols, amides, anilides, and other organic substances have been prepared; their properties have been studied and structures discussed.

Rosenheim and Schutte¹ prepared ammonium chlorotitanate $(NH_4)_2 TiCl_6 \cdot 2H_2O$ by shaking the mixture of equal quantities of ammonium chloride and hydrochloric acid solution of $TiCl_4$ and pyridino-bromotitanic acid by saturating a solution of pyridine hydrobromide and titanic acid in ethanolic hydrobromic acid. Fowles and Pollard² studied the reaction between $TiCl_4$ and liquid ammonia and obtained titanium octammine $TiCl_4 \cdot 8NH_3$. Rose³ prepared titanium tetrammine tetrachloride $TiCl_4 \cdot 4NH_3$ by saturating $TiCl_4$ with ammonia. Ruff and Eisner⁴ obtained titanium octammino-tetrabromide $TiBr_4 \cdot 8NH_3$ by the action of ammonia gas on $TiBr_4$ at a low pressure. Prasad and Tripathi⁵ prepared a number of amino derivatives of titanic bromide by the action of titanium tetrabromide on amines and heterocyclic bases.

The work has now been extended to study the effect of different co-ordinating groups on the formation of compounds in non-aqueous media.

EXPERIMENTAL

The organic compounds used were of Merck's or B. D. H. 'extra pure' quality. Titanium tetrabromide was prepared by the method of Olsen and Ryan⁶ and extracted with anhydrous ethyl acetate.

General Method of Preparation.—A dilute ethyl acetate solution of the organic substances was added to $TiBr_4$ solution in ethyl acetate with constant shaking till complete precipitation. The precipitate was filtered and washed with ethyl acetate till free of the excess of the organic compounds. It was dried at room temperature in a vacuum desiccator and analysed. Characteristics of the compounds are recorded in Table I.

Bromine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method and titanium as TiO_2 .

1. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1901, **26**, 239, 145; 1900, **24**, 236.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2588.
3. *Annalen*, 1841, **40**, 240.
4. *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 2260.
5. *This Journal*, 1956, **33**, 939; 1957, **34**, 452, 759; 1958, **35**, 415.
6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 2215.

TABLE I

Compounds.	Compounds formed.	Colour.	M.P.	%Titanium.		%Bromine.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	[Ti(NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Yellowish green	220°	5.18	5.21	34.85	34.74
<i>m</i> - "	"	Orange	*280°	5.14	5.21	34.39	34.74
<i>p</i> - "	"	Pale yellow	210°	5.26	5.21	34.30	34.74
<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	[Ti(COOH.C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	"	210°	5.21	5.24	35.32	34.93
<i>p</i> - "	"	Orange-yellow	*215°	5.29	5.24	35.32	34.93
<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	[Ti(NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .OH) ₂]Br ₄	Red	*221°	8.16	8.19	54.83	54.60
<i>m</i> - "	"	Yellow	219°	8.23	8.19	54.23	54.60
<i>p</i> - "	"	Brown	233°	8.08	8.19	54.00	54.60
Urea	[Ti(NH ₂ .CO.NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Light red	214°	7.94	7.00	53.08	52.60
Benzamide	[Ti(C ₆ H ₅ .CONH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Yellow	135°	5.58	5.83	37.49	37.53
Acetanilide	[Ti(C ₆ H ₅ .NH.COCH ₃) ₄]Br ₄	White	211°	5.31	5.28	35.05	35.24
<i>p</i> -Aminoacetanilide	[Ti(NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NH.COCH ₃) ₂]Br ₄	Pink	236°	7.22	7.18	48.72	47.89
2-Aminopyridine	[Ti(C ₅ H ₄ N.NH ₂) ₂]Br ₄	White	*254°	8.20	8.27	55.58	55.18
Diphenylbenzidine	[Ti{C ₆ H ₄ NH.C ₆ H ₅ } ₂]Br ₄	Dirty yellow	*216°	4.56	4.61	31.54	30.77
Amidophenol	[Ti(OHC ₆ H ₄ .CONH ₂) ₂]Br ₄	Brown	*137°	7.41	7.47	48.83	49.83
Biuret	[Ti(NH ₂ .CONH.CONH ₂) ₂]Br ₄	White	*207°	8.34	8.38	56.08	55.75
<i>p</i> -Aminodimethylaniline	[Ti{(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂ } ₂]Br ₄	Pink	*174°	7.53	7.49	49.44	49.99
<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine	[Ti{(C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂) ₂]Br ₄	Brown	*160°	8.25	8.21	54.17	54.79
<i>p</i> - "	[Ti{C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂ } ₂]Br ₄	Blue	*165°	8.26	8.21	53.91	54.79
8-Hydroxyquinoline	[Ti(NC ₉ H ₆ .OH) ₄]Br ₄	Orange	*180°	5.00	5.06	33.72	33.75

*Decomposition temp.

DISCUSSION

The effective atomic number of titanium in all these cases has not attained the next inert gas configuration and the compounds though stable in dry atmosphere begin to hydrolyse when exposed to moist air.

An examination of the results (Table I) shows that 4 molecules of nitroanilines, aminoacids, 8-hydroxyquinoline, urea, and acetanilide combine with one molecule of TiBr₄, indicating that NO₂, OH, and COOH groups do not take part in co-ordination. In case of urea and acetanilide, it appears that co-ordination is through CO group since it is much stronger than =NH or -NH₂ groups.

In the rest, one molecule of titanium tetrabromide combines with two molecules of organic substances and the compounds formed are fairly stable, showing thereby that chelate compounds are formed in all these cases.

It is interesting to note that only two molecules of aminophenols combine with one molecule of titanium tetrabromide, showing thereby that NH₂ and OH groups take part in the co-ordination, though OH group remains inactive in presence of NH₂ groups, as has been observed in other cases.

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